

CPW

CANCER PREVENTION at WORK

Protocols of mixed-methods study
on sociocultural, economic, and behavioural factors
Deliverable D5.1

05.2024

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*Legend = **R** – Report // **DEM** – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs // **DEC** – Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. // **DMP** – Data management plan // **OTHER** – Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

	Name of the Entity	Acronym	Role	Country	ORG Type
1	Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna	UNIBO	C	IT	RTD
2	National Institute of Public Health	INSP	B	RO	PHI
3	Romanian Society for Occupational Medicine	SRMM	B	RO	SME
4	Clinic Hospital Colentina, Bucharest	Col Hosp	B	RO	Hosp
5	Timisoara Municipal Emergency Clinical Hospital	SCMUT	B	RO	Hosp
6	Regional Authority of Public Health Banská Bystrica	RAPH BB	B	SK	PHI
7	University of Southern Denmark	SDU	B	DK	RTD
8	WEDO Project Intelligence Made Easy SI	WeDo	B	ES	SME
9	F.D. Roosevelt University General Hospital of Banská Bystrica	FDRH	B	SK	Hosp
10	Fundacion para la investigacion y la innovacion biosanitaria del Principado de Asturias	FINBA	B	ES	NGO
11	Intesa Sanpaolo SPA	ISP	B	IT	LC
12	Università di Torino	UNITO	B	IT	RTD
13					
14	Heidelberg University Hospital	UKHD	B	DE	RTD
15	RPA Europe Prague s.r.o.	RPA Prague	B	CZ	SME
16	Regione Emilia Romagna	RER	B	IT	PHI
17	Zeleziarne Podbrezova a.s.	ZP	B	SK	SME
18	ASL Città di Torino	ASL TO	B	IT	PHI
19	Health Service of the Principality of Asturias	SESPA	AP	ES	PHI

***Legend** = Role in the Project: **C** – Coordinator // **B** – Beneficiary // **AP** – Associated Partner // Organization Type: **RTD** – Research and Technological Development// **PHI** – Public Health Institution // **Hosp** – Hospital // **SME** – Small and medium-sized enterprises. // **LC** – Large Company // **NGO** – Non-Governmental Org.

Table 1. The CPW's Consortium.

	Work Packages Name	WP Leader
1	WP1 Coordination and Management	UNIBO
2	WP2 Gastric Cancer Prevention Through Helicobacter Pylori Screening and Treatment	FINBA
3	WP3 Liver Cancer Prevention Through HCV Screening and Treatment	INSP
4	WP4 Prevention of Cancers Associated with HPV Infection	RAPH BB
5	WP5 Behavioural and Sociocultural Assessment	SDU
6	WP6 Cost Effectiveness Analysis	RPA Prague
7	WP7 Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation	WEDO

Table 2. The CPW Work Packages.

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WP5 Working Group Composition		
	Entity	Acronym
1	Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna	UNIBO
2	National Institute of Public Health	INSP
3	Regional Authority of Public Health Banská Bystrica	RAPH BB
6	University of Southern Denmark	SDU
7	WEDO Project Intelligence Made Easy SI	WeDo
8	F.D. Roosevelt University General Hospital of Banská Bystrica	FDRH
9	Intesa Sanpaolo SPA	ISP
10	Università di Torino	UNITO
11	Heidelberg University Hospital	UKHD
12	RPA Europe Prague s.r.o.	RPA Prague
13	Zeleziarne Podbrezova a.s.	ZP
14	ASL Città di Torino	ASL TO

Table 3. Composition of the WP5 Working Group on sociocultural, economic, and behavioural factors.

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	7
LIST OF FIGURES	7
LIST OF TABLES	7
1 INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 PROJECT INTRODUCTION	8
1.2 OBJECTIVES AND TASKS OF WP5	9
1.3 CONTENTS OF THE DELIVERABLE D5.1	9
2 BACKGROUND	10
2.1 HEALTH CAPITAL AS AN INTEGRATIVE FRAMEWORK	10
2.2 PROJECTIVE TECHNIQUES IN HEALTH RESEARCH.....	11
2.3 FOCUS GROUP INTERVIEWS IN HEALTH RESEARCH.....	12
3 SECONDARY DATA COLLECTION FROM EXTANT LITERATURE	13
3.1 PROTOCOL FOR SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW	13
4 PRIMARY MIXED-METHODS DATA COLLECTION AT BASELINE	14
4.1 CONTRIBUTION TO JOINT BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRES.....	14
4.2 HARMONIZATION OF BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRES	15
4.3 PROTOCOL FOR SELF-ADMINISTERED PROJECTIVE TECHNIQUES AT BASELINE.....	15
5 PRIMARY QUALITATIVE DATA COLLECTION THROUGH FOCUS GROUPS	16
5.1 PROTOCOL FOR PROJECTIVE TECHNIQUES DURING FOCUS GROUPS	16
5.2 THEMATIC INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR FOCUS GROUPS	17
6 SUMMARY AND CONCLUDING REMARKS	18
APPENDIX	19
1 PROTOCOL FOR SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW	19
2 QUESTION CATALOGUE FOR BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRES	21
3 HARMONIZATION OF BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRES	36
4 PROTOCOL FOR SELF-ADMINISTERED PROJECTIVE TECHNIQUE	43
5 FINAL ENGLISH VERSION OF SELF-ADMINISTERED PROJECTIVE TECHNIQUE	49
6 FINAL ITALIAN VERSION OF SELF-ADMINISTERED PROJECTIVE TECHNIQUE	51
7 FINAL ROMANIAN VERSION OF SELF-ADMINISTERED PROJECTIVE TECHNIQUE	53
8 FINAL SLOVAK VERSION OF SELF-ADMINISTERED PROJECTIVE TECHNIQUE	55
9 PROTOCOL FOR PROJECTIVE TECHNIQUES DURING FOCUS GROUPS	58
10 THEMATIC INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR FOCUS GROUPS	64

Executive summary

This document is Deliverable 5.1 (“Protocols of mixed-methods study on sociocultural, economic, and behavioural factors”) of the CANCER PREVENTION AT WORK (CPW) project. It is issued under the responsibility of the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) with the contribution of a working group comprising principal investigators and team members from work packages WP2, WP3, and W4, as well as the project coordinator Prof. Dr. Paolo Boffetta and the project manager Alessandra Cataneo from the University of Bologna.

The objective of WP5 is to identify, assess, and address the behavioural and sociocultural barriers and facilitators of the interventions against infection-related cancers conducted in WP2-WP4. In particular, we aim to do so by identifying the barriers and facilitators of the primary prevention interventions in this project through a mixed methods study. As a part of this study, we collect:

- secondary data through a review of extant literature on sociocultural, economic, and behavioural barriers and facilitators of cancer prevention,
- primary mixed quantitative/qualitative data through the baseline questionnaires of the involved workplace and occupational cohorts, and
- primary qualitative data through focus groups with individuals from a subset of the workplace and occupational cohorts.

This study represents the first phase in a multi-phased overall study design, which is similar to one that has been successfully employed in a large study on under- and never-screened populations in the context of breast, cervical, and colorectal cancer.¹ Special care is taken to facilitate the geographically and culturally dispersed data collection.

Through the study described in deliverable D5.1, we aim to build a solid understanding of the sociocultural, economic, and behavioural factors influencing patterns of participation and non-participation in screening examinations (WP2 & WP3), patterns of hesitancy to vaccination interventions (WP4), and the patient pathways in case of positive screening results (WP2 & WP3).

¹ Gesink, D., Filsinger, B., Mihic, A., Norwood, T. A., Sarai Racey, C., Perez, D., Antal, J., Ritvo, P., & Vernich, L. (2016). Cancer screening barriers and facilitators for under and never screened populations: A mixed methods study. *Cancer Epidemiology*, 45, 126–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.canep.2016.10.015>

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CPW	Cancer Prevention at Work project
OH	Occupational health
WP	Work Package
HCQ	Health Capital Questionnaire
Hp	<i>Helicobacter Pylori</i>
HPV	Human Papilloma Virus
HCV	Hepatitis C Virus
HBV	Hepatitis B Virus

List of Figures

Figure 1. The health capital model underlying the proposed projective circle technique.

List of Tables

Table 1. The CPW's Consortium.

Table 2. The CPW Work Packages.

Table 3. Composition of the WP5 Working Group on sociocultural, economic, and behavioural factors.

Table 4. Eligibility criteria for the full-text screening phase of the systematic literature.

Table 5. Thematic interview guide.

1 Introduction

1.1 Project introduction

Chronic infections represent a major cause of human cancer: on a global scale, they are responsible for an estimated 13% of human cancers. Helicobacter pylori (Hp), Hepatitis C virus (HCV), and Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) are responsible together for 75% of these cases, or 10% of total cancer burden². Occupational health surveillance is mandatory in all European countries: although the mechanisms of its implementation vary between the countries, these programs are in general aimed at diagnosing and preventing work-related diseases. Prevention of occupational cancers has therefore been a component of Occupational health (OH) surveillance.

In recent years, however, there has been a movement towards including occupational health surveillance aspects of health promotion which are not occupational in a strict sense. This approach stems from several considerations: (i) the contact between the worker and the health professional in charge of the surveillance can be seen as a privileged opportunity for health promotion in general; (ii) through the worker, the health promotion initiative may reach other groups of the population; (iii) because of the periodic nature of the visits entailed by the occupational health surveillance, it is possible to efficiently implement follow-up mechanisms. The conceptual framework of the proposed research is based on the incorporation into preventive medical check-ups at work of primary prevention programs against Hp, HCV and HPV infections.

The overarching objectives of the proposed research are:

- to conduct a series of pilot projects aimed at assessing the effectiveness (including cost-effectiveness) of incorporating primary prevention interventions against Hp, HCV and HPV into existing occupational surveillance systems in high-risk populations, including its impact beyond the workers directly involved in the pilot projects, and
- to identify barriers and bottlenecks for the implementation of such interventions.

This action is part of the Cancer Mission cluster of projects on 'Prevention and early detection'.

² de Martel C, Georges D, Bray F, Ferlay J, Clifford GM. Global burden of cancer attributable to infections in 2018: a worldwide incidence analysis. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2020;8: e180-e190.

1.2 Objectives and tasks of WP5

The overarching objective of WP5 is to identify, assess, and address the behavioural and sociocultural barriers and facilitators of the interventions against infection-related cancers conducted in WP2, WP3 and WP4 in the context of occupational health surveillance.

The Specific Objectives of WP5 include:

- O5.1 Identify the behavioural and sociocultural barriers and facilitators of the primary prevention interventions from WP2, WP3, and WP4 through a mixed methods study of the involved workplace and occupational cohorts.
- O5.2 Develop the Health Capital Questionnaire (HCQ) for assessing barriers and facilitators of prevention programs for infection-related cancers.
- O5.3 Quantify the barriers and facilitators of prevention programs for infection-related cancer through a large-scale survey study.
- O5.4 Develop recommendations on how to address and exploit barriers and facilitators of prevention programs for infection-related cancers.

The following five tasks jointly address the four specific objectives O5.1, O5.2, O5.3, and O5.4, thereby advancing the project toward the achievement of the overarching objective:

- Task 5.1 Design and execution of the mixed-methods study on the concrete and potential behavioural and sociocultural barriers and facilitators of infection-related cancers, including question catalogues, study protocols, and interview guides.
- Task 5.2 Data analysis based on the mixed-methods data sets collected in Task 5.1, followed by theorisation focused on identifying underlying mechanisms.
- Task 5.3 Development of a questionnaire-based tool for assessing behavioural and sociocultural barriers and facilitators of prevention programs for infection-related cancers relying on the data and analyses from Tasks 5.1 and 5.2.
- Task 5.4 Survey study on barriers and facilitators based on the questionnaire developed in Task 5.3, executed jointly by the implementation centres.
- Task 5.5 Recommendations for addressing and exploiting barriers and facilitators based on the insights from Tasks 5.2 and 5.4.

1.3 Contents of the deliverable D5.1

This deliverable 5.1 contains the study protocols and supporting material that the WP5 Working Group has developed for the data collection.

Regarding the secondary data collection through a review of the extant literature on sociocultural, economic, and behavioural barriers and facilitators of cancer prevention, we present the study protocol for a systematic literature review of extant quantitative and qualitative studies of sociocultural, economic, and behavioural barriers and facilitators of cancers related to Hp, HPV, and HCV infections.

Regarding the primary mixed quantitative/qualitative data collection through the baseline questionnaires of the involved workplace and occupational cohorts, we first present the question catalogues and harmonization documents underlying the study protocols detailed in deliverables D2.1, D3.1, and D4.1 regarding the baseline questionnaire study. Then, we introduce the study protocol for projective techniques to assess the self-perceived relative importance of different health-related resources.

Regarding the primary qualitative data collection through focus groups with individuals from a subset of the workplace and occupational cohorts, we present two study protocols for focus groups. The first details a number of projective techniques designed to facilitate qualitative data collection across cultural and language barriers. The second study protocol contains the thematic interview guide used for the open-ended focus group discussions and for individual follow-up interviews.

2 Background

2.1 Health Capital as an integrative framework

In the face of the growing personalization of healthcare and increasing health inequalities, emerging perspectives of health as individualized and privatized capital seem promising to understand health-related behaviour and attitudes, in general, and illness prevention, in particular. Additionally, and arguably at least as important, such a resource-based perspective allows understanding and dealing with the heterogeneity of individuals and the diversity of workers in occupation-based interventions. This project builds on the WP5 lead's conceptualization of health capital³ to shed light on how individual resources play into barriers and facilitators of such interventions. Drawing on Bourdieusian capital theory, we define health capital as the *aggregate of the actual or potential resources possessed by a given agent that have the capacity to affect the position of agents in the social field of health*. This conceptualization is already reshaping the global academic discussion on health inequality, for example regarding the impact of diverse socioeconomic backgrounds on health practices⁴, socially-anchored gender differences in life expectancy⁵, and cross-sectional analysis of health-related behaviours⁶.

Health capital comprises those resources available to the agents that can be employed toward maintaining good health and managing illness. Such resources can be economic, social, cultural, or even symbolic in nature, including but not limited to the agents' health-related skills and competencies, their social networks and relationships, their financial means, and their social statuses. Health capital allows us to consider how economic, social, and cultural resources influence the individuals' positions in this field and their interactions with occupational-based cancer prevention interventions, health professionals, and each other.

Compared to similar conceptual frameworks such as health literacy, health capital not only allows to study the effect of accumulated health knowledge but also more complex factors such as individuals' desire for distinction within social structures. Recent work has shown how health capital can help to understand the important role of such social aspects in the context of COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy⁷. The successful application of health capital to cancer prevention requires an in-depth understanding of the mechanisms underlying the behavioural and sociocultural barriers and facilitators encountered, as well as an operationalization of health capital into an assessment tool.

The main assumption underlying this conceptual approach is that differences in the distribution of resources influence the behavioural and sociocultural barriers and facilitators of cancer prevention.

³ Schneider-Kamp, A. (2021). Health Capital: Toward a conceptual framework for understanding the construction of individual health. *Social Theory & Health*, 19(3), 205–219. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41285-020-00145-x>

⁴ McCoy, C. A., Johnston, E., & Hogan, C. (2024). The impact of socioeconomic status on health practices via health lifestyles: Results of qualitative interviews with Americans from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds. *Social Science & Medicine*, 344, 116618. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2024.116618>

⁵ Baum, F., Musolino, C., Gesesew, H. A., & Popay, J. (2021). New Perspective on Why Women Live Longer Than Men: An Exploration of Power, Gender, Social Determinants, and Capitals. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18020661>

⁶ Xu, P., & Jiang, J. (2020). Individual Capital Structure and Health Behaviors among Chinese Middle-Aged and Older Adults: A Cross-Sectional Analysis Using Bourdieu's Theory of Capitals. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(20), Article 20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17207369>

⁷ Schneider-Kamp, A. (2022). COVID-19 Vaccine Hesitancy in Denmark and Russia: A qualitative typology at the nexus of agency and health capital. *SSM - Qualitative Research in Health*, 2, 100116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmqr.2022.100116>

2.2 Projective techniques in health research

Projective techniques originate from the field of psychology, where they initially were utilized for personality assessment and evaluating personal functioning⁸. By presenting ambiguous stimuli, these techniques aim to access thoughts and feelings not easily captured through direct questioning by eliminating personalization from the questions directed at the respondent. This approach aims to reduce the respondents' sensitivity to their answers, thus minimizing their conscious defences⁹. By ambiguous stimuli and open-ended tasks, projective techniques have the potential to delve deeper than the information obtained through self-reported surveys or interviews, aiming to elicit less rational and more spontaneous responses compared to traditional qualitative approaches in the anticipation that these are more spontaneous and less influenced by response biases compared to conventional qualitative methods¹⁰.

Health researchers typically employ projective techniques to delve into sensitive topics and uncover unique perspectives, as they allow participants to express thoughts and feelings that may be difficult to access by traditional methods. In health research, they are used to explore issues such as cancer screenings in the community¹¹ or obstetrical nurses' attitudes toward medical interventions like Caesarean sections¹². This methodology proves particularly advantageous for investigating health-related subjects in diverse cultural contexts, especially where language and cultural barriers pose challenges to qualitative data collection¹³.

Since the CPW project involves workers from different cultural contexts, projective techniques represent a suitable methodology as part of our mixed-methods data collection, occupying a space in between, different from and, simultaneously, supplementing traditional quantitative and qualitative methods.

⁸ Jura, M. B. (2017). Projective Tests of Personality. In F. Volkmar (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Autism Spectrum Disorders* (pp. 1-5). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-6435-8_476-4.

⁹ Das, G. (2018). A Review on Projective Techniques applied on Social Science Research. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, 5(3), 10-14.

¹⁰ Malone, T., & Hackett, P. M. W. (2020). Projective techniques in health research. In *Handbook of Ethnography in Healthcare Research* (Chapter 27). Routledge.

¹¹ Wiehagen, T., Caito, N. M., Thompson, V. S., et al. (2007). Applying projective techniques to formative research in health communication development. *Health Promotion Practice*, 2007;8(2):164-172. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1524839906289818>

¹² Regan, M., & Liaschenko, J. (2008). In the margins of the mind: Development of a projective research methodology for the study of nursing practice. *Research and Theory for Nursing Practice: An International Journal*, 22(1), 10–23.

¹³ Sijtsema, S., Linnemann, A., Backus, G. B. C., Jongen, W., Gaasbeek, T., & Dagevos, H. (2007). Exploration of projective techniques to unravel health perception. *British Food Journal*, 109, 443-456. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00070700710753508>

2.3 Focus group interviews in health research

Focus group discussions are frequently employed as a qualitative research approach to delve into social issues at a deeper level¹⁴ than questionnaires and even structured interviews allow. Focus groups go beyond simple group interviews, as they involve in-depth group discussions facilitated by a trained moderator. They facilitate focusing on specific topics in a semi-structured or unstructured manner, allowing depth similar to individual in-depth interviews with the added possibility of cross-fertilizing group reflections.

Focus groups entail informal discussions among selected individuals, providing valuable insights on one or multiple pre-determined topics¹⁵. Powell and Single¹⁶ define focus groups as assemblies of individuals convened by researchers to share personal experiences on the research subject. The distinguishing feature of focus groups is the rich insights and data generated through participant interaction¹⁷. Focus groups are a qualitative method that has been successfully applied in health and cancer research, for example, when studying breast, prostate, gynaecologic, liver, and blood cancer patients^{18,19,20,21}. Therefore, focus groups are a suitable methodological approach to explore workers' perceptions of self-perceived health capital and patient pathways to cancer prevention.

¹⁴ Nyumba, T., Wilson, T., Derrick, C., & Mukherjee, N. (2018). The use of focus group discussion methodology: Insights from two decades of application in conservation. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 9, 20-32. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12860>

¹⁵ Gundumogula, M. (2020). Importance of focus groups in qualitative research. *The International Journal of Humanities & Social Studies*, 8(11), 299-302.

¹⁶ Powell, R. A., Single, H. M., & Lloyd, K. R. (1996). Focus groups in mental health research: Enhancing the validity of user and provider questionnaires. *International Journal of Social Psychology*, 42(3), 193-206.

¹⁷ Sagoe, D. (2012). Precincts and prospects in the use of focus groups in social and behavioral science research. *The Qualitative Report*, 17, Article 29, 1-16.

¹⁸ Ellis, P. M., & Butow, P. N. (1998). Focus group interviews examining attitudes to randomised trials among breast cancer patients and the general community. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health*, 22(5), 528-531. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-842X.1998.tb01432.x>

¹⁹ Frazier, L. M., Miller, V. A., Horbelt, D. V., Delmore, J. E., Miller, B. E., & Paschal, A. M. (2010). Comparison of focus groups on cancer and employment conducted face to face or by telephone. *Qualitative Health Research*, 20(5), 617-627. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732310361466>

²⁰ Furumaya, A., Nooijen, L. E., Haring, M. P. D., et al. (2022). Development of a set of patient-reported outcome measures for patients with benign liver tumours and cysts: Patient focus groups and systematic review. *Journal of Patient-Reported Outcomes*, 6, 124. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41687-022-00531-1>

²¹ Smith, S. K., Wiltshire, G., Brown, F. F., et al. (2022). 'You're kind of left to your own devices': A qualitative focus group study of patients with breast, prostate or blood cancer at a hospital in the South West of England, exploring their engagement with exercise and physical activity during cancer treatment and in the months following standard care. *BMJ Open*, 12, e056132. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-056132>

3 Secondary data collection from extant literature

A preliminary literature search in three databases (WebOfScience, PubMed, Scopus) identified 685 potentially relevant publications, indicating a small but not insignificant body of literature on sociocultural, economic, and behavioural barriers and facilitators of cancer prevention. This indicates the potential for a systematic literature review to inform our study. In the following, we present the study protocol for a systematic literature review of extant quantitative and qualitative studies of sociocultural, economic, and behavioural barriers and facilitators of cancers related to at least Hp, HPV, and HCV infections. The detailed search strategy, including keywords, the time frame of publications, and the inclusion criteria used for the systematic literature review, are presented in the protocol described in the following subsection and included as **Appendix 1**.

3.1 Protocol for systematic literature review

The protocol for the systematic literature review was developed according to the PRISMA 2020 guidelines²². We developed the search terms in an iterative process with the clinical partners, drawing upon their expertise to ensure adequate coverage without being overwhelmed by the sheer amount of search results. Following best practices, we pre-specified the eligibility criteria for maximizing scientific rigour.

The eligibility criteria were carefully crafted to ensure relevance to the scope of the CPW project. That said, we decided to include infections with the Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) after a preliminary search indicated that HCV and HBV often co-occur in studies. In addition, while HCV is the main driver of liver cancer, HBV infections do contribute significantly to the overall cancer burden.

²² Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *International Journal of Surgery*, *88*, 105906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsu.2021.105906>

4 Primary mixed-methods data collection at baseline

As part of the interventions aiming at cancer prevention performed in WP2, WP3, and WP4, the workplace and occupational cohorts are assessed at baseline through questionnaires. To ensure the quality of the data collected, the main part of the questionnaire is administered by others, while only sensitive or optional questions are self-administered.

In this section, we first present the question catalogues and harmonization documents underlying the study protocols for the baseline questionnaires detailed in deliverables D2.1, D3.1, and D4.1. The baseline questions specific to WP5 are integrated into the questionnaires developed for WP2, WP3, and WP4. Thus, the sample is the union of the samples for the baseline data collection of WP2, WP3, and WP4.

In the remainder of this section, we introduce the study protocol for projective techniques to assess the self-perceived relative importance of different health-related resources. The sample for this more qualitative part of the data collection is a subset of the sample for the baseline data collection, with the choice to integrate the projective techniques into the baseline data collection depending on the individual implementation centres.

4.1 Contribution to joint baseline questionnaires

In WP5, we created a catalogue of questions (cf **Appendix 2**) to be included in the development of the baseline questionnaires for the interventions in WP2, WP3, and WP4. This catalogue was meant to serve as a coordinated source of inspiration to supplement the baseline questionnaires with questions regarding the sociocultural, economic, and behavioural aspects of the health practices of the workplace and occupational cohorts. The leaders of WP2, WP3, and WP4 were invited together with the leads of the implementation centres to select relevant questions from the catalogue and integrate them into the sections of their baseline questionnaire where they fit best. The WP5 Working Group collaborated with WP2, WP3, and WP4 on identifying the most relevant questions and adapting them for inclusion in the respective baseline questionnaire. In the catalogue in the appendix, WP5-specific questions are marked in blue.

The questions included in the catalogue comprise both general and specific questions related to individuals' social, economic, cultural, and behavioural antecedents. The collaborating partners were instructed on the need that, when integrating questions into the baseline questionnaire, they need to translate the questions to the local context in order to maximize utility and avoid cultural and language-specific misunderstanding among the members of the target cohorts. Additionally, there is also a need for differentiation between, for example, health professionals and factory workers, which might require awareness and a reflective approach to adapting the questions. Finally, the possible options for answering had to be adjusted in the case of some of the questions, as reasonable options heavily depend on the context. Similarly, questions regarding ethnicity and language proficiency are highly context-dependent. The main ethnic groups for each context had to be identified and supplemented by an "Other – please specify" option. The languages spoken in the context (such as official languages and other common minority languages) should be specified and supplemented by an "Other – please specify" option. The household income should be stated in descriptive or (preferably) numeric terms describing intervals commonly associated with household income in the context and currency.

4.2 Harmonization of baseline questionnaires

The WP5 Working Group took on the task of harmonizing the three baseline questionnaires developed by WP2, WP3, and WP4. The draft versions of these baseline questionnaires were reviewed by all collaborating partners, and suggestions for improvement were given. Then WP5 compared the updated versions of baseline questionnaires of WP2, WP3, and WP4 in terms of both general questions, WP-independent questions, and sociocultural, economic, and behavioural questions. We did not attempt to harmonize the WP-specific questions related to the focus infection type.

The comparison of the remaining bulk of questions was performed by determining which of the pairs of questions in the WP2, WP3, and WP4 draft questionnaires coincided, were similar, or differed significantly. Based on this analysis, we drafted suggestions for harmonization of the baseline questionnaires (cf. **Appendix 3**). These suggestions were presented to the partners active in WP2, WP3, and WP4. WP5-specific questions to assess sociocultural, economic, and behavioural aspects of treating and preventing infections related to cancer at the workplace were carefully developed by the WP5 Working Group. We recommended the inclusion of a common subset of these questions in the three baseline questionnaires to ensure universal coverage of at least the most foundational aspects relevant to the behavioural and sociocultural assessment of barriers and facilitators of cancer prevention. Ultimately, the harmonization ensured that the aims and the context of each of WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5 will be covered.

4.3 Protocol for self-administered projective techniques at baseline

The second objective O5.2 of WP5 is to develop the Health Capital Questionnaire (HCQ) for assessing barriers and facilitators of prevention programs for infection-related cancers. As a first part of the qualitative part of the data collection in our study, we developed the study protocol for including a projective technique to assess worker's self-perceived health capital at baseline (cf. **Appendix 4**), i.e., as part of the cross-WP data collection on-going in WP2, WP3, and WP4.

We opted to develop the projective circle technique to explore workers' perceptions of the social, cultural, and economic resources, as well as personal antecedents constituting their health capital. The projective circle technique is a self-administered technique that facilitates qualitative data collection across different cultural backgrounds. While designing the projective technique, we reflected on the likely information processing abilities and preferences among different workplace and occupational cohorts. We strived to make the projective technique maximally accessible to both those who are more focused on text perception and to those who are more focused on visualization. We collect the data with the purpose of identifying the subjective importance of different workplace and occupational cohorts' health capital-related resources and antecedents. Furthermore, we would like to identify possible correlations and associations between health capital resources and antecedents on the one hand, and sociodemographic and behavioural variables on the other hand. The projective circle technique will be employed together as part of the baseline questionnaire data collection in collaboration with those partners that have the capacity to include the technique in the baseline data collection.

Finally, we created detailed user-friendly instructions for the members of the participating cohorts in English. WeDo as part of WP7 assisted the WP5 Working Group in an iterative collaboration with the design of the English reference instructions (cf. **Appendix 5**), providing black-and-white and colour versions, as well as landscape and portrait versions. As of the writing of deliverable D5.1, the instructions for the projective circle technique are undergoing language decentralised translation and cultural adaption, if needed, for deployment in the different implementation centres. To exemplify these translated and adapted instructions for the projective circle technique, we include the Italian (cf. **Appendix 6**), Romanian (cf. **Appendix 7**), and Slovak (cf. **Appendix 8**) versions, together with the English reference instructions covering the three dominant European language groups (Romance, Slavic, and Germanic languages).

5 Primary qualitative data collection through focus groups

Regarding the primary qualitative data collection through focus groups with individuals from a subset of the workplace and occupational cohorts, we present two study protocols for focus groups. The first details a number of projective techniques designed to facilitate qualitative data collection across cultural and language barriers. The second study protocol contains the thematic interview guide used for the open-ended focus group discussions and for individual follow-up interviews.

5.1 Protocol for projective techniques during focus groups

To further work towards objective O5.2, i.e., the development of the Health Capital Questionnaire (HCQ) for assessing barriers and facilitators of prevention programs for infection-related cancers, as a second part, we developed the study protocol for projective techniques to assess worker's self-perceived health capital and pathways to cancer prevention through focus groups. As mentioned above, projective techniques are used in varying degrees in health research since they allow participants to express those thoughts and feelings that can be difficult to access by direct questioning, making them particularly well-suited as a methodology for research on health-related topics in diverse cultural settings, particularly in those settings where more traditional qualitative data collection might prove difficult because of language barriers.

The study population consists of cohorts from WP2, WP3, and WP4. We will utilize a combination of purposive and convenience sampling to assemble focus groups from various cohorts, purposively aiming for maximizing participation of workers with different occupational and cultural backgrounds and recruiting those that are willing to participate. These focus groups are executed jointly by local representatives from the implementation centres and members of the WP5 team. The former contribute their expertise regarding the cohort and local language and culture while the latter contribute their expertise in qualitative health research methods.

The second study protocol on projective techniques (cf. **Appendix 9**) includes, but is not limited to, association, ordering, and expression tasks. We intend to integrate these tasks into focus groups as a qualitative method to further our understanding of barriers and facilitators for infection-related cancer prevention among the diverse workplace and occupational cohorts. We also aim to shed light on their paths of health-related behaviour and decision-making process in the context of the prevention and treatment of infections related to cancer. The qualitative data collected in the focus groups through the projective techniques will be used as another source for the development of the health capital questionnaire in addition to secondary data from Section 3, and the primary quantitative and qualitative data from Section 4. The WP5 Working Group will implement the focus groups in close collaboration with partners from WP2, WP3, and WP4 able to provide access to members of the workplace and occupational cohorts at their implementation centres. The implementation centres will provide the facilities to host the focus group data collection activities.

5.2 Thematic interview guide for focus groups

The WP5 Working Group compiled a thematic guide designed to assist in both facilitated group discussions during the focus groups and in facilitating reliable a posteriori individual follow-up interviews with members of the workplace and occupational cohorts, typically those participating in the focus groups. For obtaining candidate themes, in the first phase of the development of the interview guide, we drew upon a number of sources. First, we compiled candidate themes from the questions in the WP5-specific questions for the baseline questionnaires. Second, we distilled candidate themes from the first insights gleaned from the preliminary results of the systematic literature review conducted for the collection of secondary data on barriers and facilitators of the prevention and treatment of infections related to cancers. Third and last, we reflected on discussions with various partners from the CPW project, refining and nuancing the candidate themes potentially relevant in the prevention and treatment of infections related to cancer as presented in **Table 5**.

In the second phase of the development of the thematic interview guide, we organized the candidate themes into coherent themes and potential discussion topics under each theme, providing a foundation for the creation of more detailed interview guidelines tailored to the needs and peculiarities of specific workplace or occupational cohorts. The resulting thematic interview guide (cf. **Appendix 10**) will play a crucial role both in facilitating the focus groups and in refining interview guidelines during the later stages of qualitative data collection within the project framework, enabling us to assess more nuanced perceptions of the interventions carried out by the partners in the implementation centres.

6 Summary and concluding remarks

The CANCER PREVENTION AT WORK (CPW), funded by EU Horizon Europe and led by the University of Bologna, investigates the potential of employing occupational health surveillance to reduce the incidence of infection-related cancers, specifically through screening, treatment, and prevention of infections with *Helicobacter pylori* (Hp), Hepatitis C Virus (HCV), and Human Papilloma Virus (HPV).

The WP5 Working Group, led by the University of Southern Denmark has developed a mixed-methods approach combining quantitative and qualitative data collection methods to study the sociocultural, economic, and behavioural barriers and facilitators of cancer prevention in the context of occupational health surveillance. This approach has been described in detail in this deliverable D5.1. This deliverable also contains six study protocols for the different elements of the first phase of the mixed-methods study of WP5:

- a systematic literature review for secondary data collection,
- WP5-specific questions and the projective circle technique for the baseline questionnaires for WP2, WP3, and WP4, and
- focus group discussions with members of the workplace and occupational cohorts based on projective techniques and thematic interview guides.

The comprehensive data collected by WP5 is expected to uncover the significance of sociocultural, economic, and behavioural barriers and facilitators on health behaviours, particularly in relation to the prevention of infection-related cancers such as gastric, liver, and cervical cancer. These insights are crucial in designing targeted cancer prevention campaigns that take their onset in the health-related resources of individual citizens, i.e., in their health capital, but have the potential to be adapted and applied across various workplace and occupational settings in different cultural and geographic contexts.

Appendix

1 Protocol for systematic literature review

We aim to identify, aggregate, and validate social, cultural, economic, and personal barriers and facilitators related to the prevention of cancers related to Hp, HCV, and HPV infections. Here, by prevention, we refer to both intended and actualized participation in screening, vaccination, and eradication programs for such infections. To achieve this aim, we will conduct a systematic review of the pertinent literature. The review will be conducted and reported following PRISMA 2020 guidelines²³ with the aim of fuelling a qualitative data synthesis inspired by Le Guen et al.'s²⁴ work on barriers to hormonal contraception.

We search all records from Web of Science, PubMed, and Scopus databases published during the ten years from 2013 to 2023 using a combination of carefully selected keywords crafted jointly with the clinical project partners, who are experts in the epidemiology of infection-related cancers:

```
[HPV OR hepatitis B OR hepatitis C OR Helicobacter pylori] AND  
[prevent* OR vaccin* OR screen* OR treatm* OR eradicat*] AND  
[social OR sociocultur* OR cultur* OR econom* OR behavior* OR behaviour*]
```

First, we screen based on title and abstract, excluding articles that were not original, involved neither HPV, Hp, HBV, or HCV infections, were not related to prevention activities such as screening, vaccination, or treatment of infections related to cancer, were written in a language other than English, or insufficiently engage with social, cultural, economic, and personal barriers and facilitators. Then, we subject the remaining articles to a full-text analysis based on the pre-specified eligibility criteria presented in **Table 4**.

²³ Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *International Journal of Surgery*, 88, 105906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsu.2021.105906>

²⁴ Le Guen, M., Schantz, C., Régnier-Loilier, A., & de La Rochebrochard, E. (2021). Reasons for rejecting hormonal contraception in Western countries: A systematic review. *Social Science & Medicine*, 284, 114247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114247>

Eligibility criteria	Specifications
<i>Participants</i>	<p>Participants representing the population in general. Without severe physical or mental/intellectual disabilities. Participants with some other special conditions such as being pregnant, having addictions, noncommunicable diseases, or other chronic conditions.</p> <p>We refrain from restricting the context to high-income countries as studies set in low- and middle-income countries can be expected to deepen our understanding of the social, cultural, economic, and behavioural factors related to cancer prevention.</p>
<i>Participants' age</i>	<p>The mean age of participants is > 25 and < 65 years; Studies, where the mean age of the participants is below 25 years old and above 65 years old are excluded. The rationale behind this criterion is to limit the scope to social, cultural, economic, and personal barriers and facilitators of intended and actual participation, excluding populations groups such as children or adults in need of care where the intention and decision-making often lies with secondary parties such as parents, family members, or other guardians.</p>
<i>Perspective</i>	<p>This study focuses on the perspective of the workers/people from the general population. Therefore, we include only studies that investigated the preventive behaviour or intention to perform such behaviour from the participants' own perspective.</p> <p>We exclude studies that investigated the preventive behaviour from the perspective of secondary parties such as parents, healthcare providers, or general practitioners but not the direct recipients of infection-related preventive measures.</p>
<i>Cancer-related infections</i>	<p>Only records related to Helicobacter pylori, Hepatitis B and Hepatitis C, and HPV are included. The rationale is that (a) the related gastric, liver, and cervical cancers account for over 3 out of 4 of infection-related cancers (b) there are viable prevention strategies for these cancers.</p>
<i>Medical history</i>	<p>We are interested in preventive behaviour of specific cancer-related infections. Therefore, we exclude studies where participants were previously diagnosed with liver, gastric, or HPV infection-related cancer such cervical or throat cancer.</p>
<i>Original research</i>	<p>We exclude review articles, editorials, opinion, and theoretical articles, as well as commentaries and other non-empirical articles.</p>
<i>Language</i>	<p>We exclude articles written in languages other than English from the analysis.</p>
<i>Quality</i>	<p>We exclude articles that do not provide sufficient details regarding their methodological and analytical frameworks or where the constructs analysed were not clearly defined and explained.</p>

Table 4. Eligibility criteria for the full-text screening phase of the systematic literature.

2 Question catalogue for baseline questionnaires

CPW BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRE (WP5 SPECIFIC QUESTIONS IN BLUE)

Identification data

The identification number should be used for the questionnaire and for any biological samples.

ID number

Country ID_
center acronym_
number _____
subject status_

Example:
 RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001 = index subject from Colentina Hospital, Romania, recruited for HCV
 RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001_01 = family member of the RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001, recruited for HCV
 Note: in case of one subject included in multiple interventions we need to redefine the ID format

For local use only – information won't be entered in CPW database

Address:

.....

Telephone:

Email:

Full name of subject:

Interviewer name

Date of interview: |_|_| /|_|_| /|_|_| ||_|_| | (DD/MM/YYYY)

Subject status: |_|_|

0=non-eligible

1=index participant (worker)

2=participant (family member)

3=refusal

If "3" please explain reason of refusal.....

Part 1: General information

1.1 Sex (1=male, 2=female, 3=other/undisclosed) |__|

1.2 Ethnicity (codes to be defined) |__|__|

If other specify

Note to contributing study sites: list of ethnic groups to be defined locally.

1.3 Which languages do you speak and at what level?

(0 = not at all; 1 = basic proficiency; 2 = good proficiency; 3 = mother tongue)

Language 1 |__|

Language 2 |__|

Language 3 |__|

If other specify

Note to contributing study sites: list of languages to be defined locally according to prevalent populations and minorities.

1.2 Date of birth

Day|__|__|Month |__|__|Year |__|__||__|__| or (if date of birth not available, or not transferable):

|__|__| Age

1.3 Highest education completed |__|

0=none

1=primary

2=secondary

3=higher

9=Unknown/refuse to answer

1.4 Age at completion of full time education |__|__|

1.5 Residence |__|

1= rural

2=urban

1.6 Household income

0=low

1=low-to-middle

2=middle

3=middle-to-high

4=high

NB: Needs to be adapted to the local context, either by terms that are well-understood or by concrete amounts. Preferably concrete amounts, but this might be less acceptable in some contexts.

Part 2: Body size & self-reported health status

2.1 How tall are you?

||| cm

2.2 How much do you weigh?

||| kg

2.3 What is the most you have ever weighed?

[For women: Do not include any times when you were pregnant.]

|| kg

2.4 How much did you weigh when you were 20 years old?

|| kg

2.5 How much did you weigh about 2 years ago?

|| kg2.6 Have you recently experienced any involuntary/unexplained weight loss?

0=No; 1=Yes; 9=Unknown

2.7 Which statement would best describe your health status?

 I generally feel absolutely healthy. I only experience minor health issues from time to time. I have major and/or chronic health issues. I am constantly sick.

Please specify what health issues you experience

2.8 Would you describe yourself as a person that cares for their own health?

(0 = No; 1 = Somewhat; 2 = Yes)

2.9 Which statement would best describe your understanding of health, health practices, and health issues?

 I am fully aware of my health issues and also have a solid understanding of other health matters. I am fully aware of my health issues, their causes, and how I should take care of myself. I understand I have some health issues, but I don't know exactly why and what to do about it. My doctor tells me that I have severe health issues, but I do not really understand what it means and what I should do with this.

Part 3: Medical history

3.1 Have you ever had any of the following diseases/conditions confirmed by a doctor? |__|
(0=definitely or probably No; 1=definitely or probably Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes:

When it was first diagnosed (year, approximately)?

Were you prescribed a treatment by a doctor? (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

[To interviewer – if treatment for HCV is ongoing, the subject is ineligible]

		Year	Treatment
3.1.1	Diabetes	__ __ __ __	__
3.1.2	Hepatitis B	__ __ __ __	__
3.1.3	Hepatitis C	__ __ __ __	__
3.1.4	Hepatitis D	__ __ __ __	__
3.1.5	HIV	__ __ __ __	__
3.1.6	Sexual transmitted infections (including HPV)	__ __ __ __	__
3.1.7	Renal failure	__ __ __ __	__
3.1.8	Hematological disorders	__ __ __ __	__
3.1.9	Organ, tissue, cell transplant	__ __ __ __	__
3.1.10	Cancer If yes: site of origin __ __ (1=mouth or pharynx, 2=oesophagus, 3=stomach, 4=colon or rectum, 5=pancreas, 6=liver, 7=larynx, 8=lung, 9=melanoma, 10=breast, 11=cervix of uterus, 12=other uterus, 13=prostate, 14=bladder, 15=kidney, 16=thyroid gland, 17=leukaemia and lymphoma, 18=other, unknown or more than one site)	__ __ __ __	__

3.2 Have you ever had blood transfusion?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year):

3.3 Have you ever had treatment with blood derivatives/component?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year):

3.4 Have you ever had dialysis treatment?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year):

3.5 Have you ever had endoscopic procedures? (e.g. colonoscopy, esophagus-gastro-duodenoscopy, bronchoscopy, arthroscopy, etc.)?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year):

3.6 Have you ever had Intramuscular or intravenous administration of any substance with non-sterile syringes/devices?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year):

3.7 Have you ever had Acupuncture with non-disposable devices?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year):

3.8 Have you ever had tattoos or piercing?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes, when you donated blood last time (year):

3.9 Are you blood donor?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes, when you donated blood last time (year):

3.10 Have you ever had dental treatment, intervention or dental surgery?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was the last one (year):

3.11 Have you ever been incarcerated?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was (year):

3.12 Have you ever living in an enclosure?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes, when it was (year):

Part 4: Family history

4.1 Please list the number of brothers, sisters, sons and daughters that you have (exclude step-brothers and step-sisters):

Brothers | | Sisters | | Sons | | Daughters | |

4.2 Did any of your close relatives (those listed above plus your parents), living in the same household, ever suffer from Hepatitis B, C, D? |__|
(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

4.3 Did any of your close relatives (those listed above plus your parents) ever suffer from cancer? |__|
(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer).

If yes:

Relative (code 1-6) 1=Father 2=Mother 3=Brother 4=Sister 5=Son 6=Daughter	Age at diagnosis	Cancer site (text)	Cancer site (ICD-10 code)
__	__ __		C __ __ . __
__	__ __		C __ __ . __
__	__ __		C __ __ . __

Part 5: Civil status & household situation

5.1 What is your relationship status?

- single
- married
- cohabitating with a partner (but not married)
- divorced
- widowed
- prefer not to disclose

5.2 Who do you cohabit with, i.e., who are you living with in one household? Please indicate the numbers for each category.

- Partner/spouse
- Children
- Parents
- Other relatives
- Friends
- Flatmates/roommates (that do not qualify as friends)

5.3 When you have health issues, who do you discuss these with? Multiple answers allowed.

- Occupational specialist at work
- Family doctor or other healthcare professional
- Partner/spouse
- Children
- Parents
- Other relatives
- Friends

5.4 Who do you trust most to discuss health issues with? Multiple answers allowed.

- Occupational specialist at work
- Family doctor or other healthcare professional
- Partner/spouse
- Children
- Parents
- Other relatives
- Friends

Part 6: Tobacco and drugs

5.1 Did you smoke cigarettes in the past year? |__|

(0=No, 1=Yes, 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

5.1.1 How many cigarettes per day on average? (ignore pipe or cigar smoking; "cigarettes" include handrolled) |__|__|

5.1.2 At what age did you start smoking? (i.e. using cigarettes on most days) |__|__|

5.1.3 How many years have you smoked? |__|__|

If no:

5.1.4 Have you ever smoked cigarettes on most days for at least one year? (0=No,1=Yes, 9=refuse to answer)

5.1.5 How many cigarettes did you smoke per day on average? (ignore pipe and cigar smoking; "cigarettes" include handrolled) |__|__|

5.1.6 At what age did you start smoking on most days? |__|__|

5.1.7 At what age did you stop smoking? |__|__|

5.2 Have you ever used drugs? |__|

(0=No, 1=Yes, 9=refuse to answer)

If yes, please specify:

5.2.1 |__|__| Age when first used

5.2.2 |__|__| Age when last used

5.2.3 |__|__| Route of administration (check all that apply) :

1-Inhaling;

2-Eating;

3-Injection;

4-Other

Part 7: Alcohol drinking habits

6.1 Do you drink any alcohol? |__|
(0=No, 1=Yes, 9=Refuse to answer)

If yes:

6.1.1 How many days per week would you have some alcohol? |__|(0-7) (0 means none in most weeks)

6.1.2 How much of the following alcoholic beverages do you usually drink per week?

To interviewer: If a range is given (eg 2 or 3 bottles) then enter the upper end of the range. 0=None at all

6.1.2.1 Whiskey/vodka or other strong drinks (40% ethanol)

Quantity/week : |__|__ ||__|__ | Unit : glasses bottles

6.1.2.2 Wine

Quantity/week : |__|__ ||__|__ | Unit : glasses bottles

6.1.2.3 Beer

|__|__ ||__|__ | bottles/week

Note to contributing study sites: "glasses", i.e. standard drink volume, and "bottle" volumes to be defined locally.

Part 8: Diet

8.1 How often do you usually eat the following food items?

1=never

2=less than once a month 3=1-3 times a month 4=once or twice a week

5=most days but not every days 6=every day

9=unknown/refuse to answer

Red meat (i.e. beef, veal, pork, lamb, mutton, horse, and goat meat) If red meat consumed:

Poultry (i.e. chicken and turkey)

Processed* meat, including hams, salami, sausages, etc.

Fish

Fresh fruits (i.e. apples, pears, orange and other citrus fruits, bananas, berries, etc.)

Raw vegetables (i.e. green salads, tomatoes, etc., when in season)

Cooked green/leafy vegetables (i.e. spinach, artichokes, asparagus, green beans, etc.)

Dairy products (i.e. milk, yoghurts, cheese, butter, etc.)

Cookies, biscuits, chocolates, cakes and sweets

Soft drinks (eg cola)

*Salted, smoked, or processed with any other preservation method.

8.2. Would you describe your diet as healthy?

(0 = No; 1 = Somewhat; 2 = Yes)

8.3 Which of the following foods would you consider as healthy? Multiple answers encouraged.

Red meat (i.e. beef, veal, pork, lamb, mutton, horse, and goat meat) If red meat consumed:

Poultry (i.e. chicken and turkey)

Processed* meat, including hams, salami, sausages, etc.

Fish

Fresh fruits (i.e. apples, pears, orange and other citrus fruits, bananas, berries, etc.)

Raw vegetables (i.e. green salads, tomatoes, etc., when in season)

Cooked green/leafy vegetables (i.e. spinach, artichokes, asparagus, green beans, etc.)

Dairy products (i.e. milk, yoghurts, cheese, butter, etc.)

Cookies, biscuits, chocolates, cakes and sweets

Soft drinks (eg cola)

8.4 When you buy groceries, which statement best describes your buying behaviour?

I avoid organic products.

I go for the cheapest options, no matter whether they are organic or not.

I would pay a bit more for organic products.

I buy only organic products when available.

Part 9: Reproductive history and sexual habits

For all subjects

9.1 How many partners did you have in total? |__|__ |

Women |__|__ |

Men |__|__ |

9.2 Did you have unprotected sex with unknown partners? |__|

(0=No, 1=Yes, 9=Refuse to answer)

9.3 Have you ever been vaccinated against Hepatitis B? |__|

(0=No, 1=Yes, 9=Unknown/Refuse to answer)

If yes:

9.3.1 When did you received the last dose of vaccine?

year |__|__ ||__|__ |

age |__|__ |

9.4 Have you ever been vaccinated against Human Papilloma Virus?

9.4.1 If yes, when did you get the vaccine?

year |__|__ ||__|__ |

age |__|__ |

Only for women

9.3 Are you pregnant now? |__|

(0=No, 1=Yes, 9=Refuse to answer)

9.4 Have you ever been pregnant? (Please consider pregnancies that lasted at least 5 months) |__|

(0=No, 1=Yes, 9=Refuse to answer)

If yes:

9.4.1 How many babies have you had? (Please consider babies born alive or dead after 5 months pregnancy) |__|__ |

Part 10: Occupational history

Please list below any occupations or jobs you have held for at least 10 years. If you had more than one occupation for 10 years or more, then start with the first job you had after you left school.

Note: should we consider also jobs lasting less than 10 years?

OCCUPATION NUMBER |__|

10.1 From: year | | | | | to year | | | | | and/or

From: age | | | to age | | |

10.2 Occupation / Job title:

.....

10.3 Main activity of the company [if self-employed, state so]:

.....

.....

10.4 Your main type of activity at this job:

.....

10.5 Were you exposed to any biological hazards (human tissue, organs, blood, biological fluids, etc) ? |__|

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=Don't know)

If yes:

10.5.1 Have you received OHS training? |__|

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=refuse to answer/Don't know)

10.5.2 Do you wear personal protective equipment? |__|

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9= refuse to answer/Don't know)

10.5.3 Did you experience any injury with biological contamination risk (prick, cut, etc.)? |__|

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9= refuse to answer/Don't know)

[Repeat above questions for as many occupations as necessary]

Part 11: Non occupational physical and spiritual activity

This question relates to your physical activity habits at home or for leisure (include walking for exercise, running, swimming gym, team sports). Even if this was in the past, please include it.

11.1 Do/did you exercise regularly (at least 30 mins per week)? |

(0) Never; (1) Yes, still; (2) Yes, only in the past; (9) unknown/refuse to answer

If yes (current and past)

11.1.2 How often is/was it?

11.1.2.1 | | Number of times per week

11.1.2.2 | | How long is/was it? (min each time)

11.1.2.3 |How intensive is/was it?

1 = Low=no increase in heart beat, and no perspiration

2 = Moderate=increase the heart beat slightly with some light perspiration

3 = Vigorous= increase the heart beat substantially with heavy sweating

11.2 Are/were you physically active daily due to household activities, such as grocery shopping and supplying the house with first needs, looking after children, gardening, etc. (at least two hours per day)? |

(0) Never; (1) Yes, still; (2) Yes, only in the past; (9) unknown/refuse to answer

11.3 On a typical day, how much hours do you spend (from when you wake up until you go to bed) doing the following?

| | Watching television/videos

| | Playing computer/video games

| | Sitting while listening to music or reading

| | Consuming content on mobile phones (e.g. social media apps)

11.4 Which of the following statements describe your situation? Multiple answers allowed.

| I am member of a fitness club/studio.

| I have access to fitness equipment at home.

| I exercise regularly under professional guidance.

| I exercise regularly in a group.

| None of the above.

11.5 Is religious/spiritual practice important to you? |

(0) Never; (1) Yes, still; (2) Yes, only in the past; (9) unknown/refuse to answer

If yes (current and past)

11.1.2 How often is/was it?

11.1.2.1 | | Number of times per week

11.1.2.2 | | How long is/was it? (min each time)

11.1.2.3 |At what level do you usually practice?

1 = Individual

2 = Family

3 = Social network

4 = Organized events

Part 12: Opinion on HCV testing and cancer prevention at workplace**Note: this section needs to be revised in close cooperation with WP5, WP6**

Before entering this study was you aware of the risk factors for liver cancer?

0=no

1=yes

9=refuse to answer

Before entering this study was you aware of the risks of HCV infection?

0=no

1=yes

9=refuse to answer

If yes, from where did you get the information:

 GP physician Occupational health physician Other physician Colleagues/ friends Social media Mass media (TV, Radio, papers) other

(only for those not diagnosed in the past with the disease)

Have you ever been tested for viral hepatitis?

0=no

1=yes

9= refuse to answer/Don't know

If yes:

When / / (DD/MM/YYYY)

What type of test it was?

 for hepatitis B for hepatitis C I do not remember/ I do not know

Where did you get tested:

 GP physician Occupational health physician otherDid you paid for the test?

0=no

1=yes

9= I do not remember/ I do not know

Are you in favor of carrying out the HCV testing in the workplace?

0=no

1=yes

9=refuse to answer

Do you think this will make it easier to implement?

0=no
1=yes
9=refuse to answer

Do you think you were given adequate information before taking the screening test? |__|

0=no
1=yes
9=refuse to answer

If you test positive for HCV, would you be inclined to undergo antiviral therapy? |__|

0=no
1=yes
9=refuse to answer

3 Harmonization of baseline questionnaires

Questions suggested for inclusion in the final baseline questionnaire version for WP2 to harmonize with WP3, and WP4

- Marital status. Please kindly add cohabitation (Living with a partner but not married) as a separate option to the possible answers.
- Source of health information seeking
-
- Where do you obtain information about health from? Multiple answers allowed.
- Occupational specialist at work
- Family doctor or other healthcare professional
- Close network such as friends and relatives
- Online information (excluding social media)
- Social media platforms (for ex., Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Instagram, etc.)
-
- Diet.
- Would it be possible for you to divide the question regarding the vegetables to 2 questions? We recommend one question to be about tinned vegetables and the other about fresh and frozen vegetables. In case it is not so important for you maybe you can leave only fresh and frozen vegetables option. Please also kindly mention that potatoes should be excluded while reporting vegetable intake. This is regarding WHO guidelines for fruits and vegetables intake.

WP5 Specific Questions

1. Would you describe your diet as healthy?
0 = No; 1 = Somewhat; 2 = Yes
2. Which statement would best describe your health status?
 I generally feel absolutely healthy.
 I only experience minor health issues from time to time.
 I have major and/or chronic health issues.
 I am constantly sick.
3. Which statement would best describe your understanding of health, health practices, and health issues?
 - I am fully aware of my health issues and also have a solid understanding of other health matters.
 - I am fully aware of my health issues, their causes, and how I should take care of myself.
 - I understand I have some health issues, but I don't know exactly why and what to do about it.
 - My doctor tells me that I have severe health issues, but I do not really understand what it means and what I should do with this.
4. Do you have savings/financial funds that (in case of losing your income) could cover your expenses for at least 3 subsequent months?
0=No 1=Yes
5. Do you have a group of close friends you feel you belong to?
0=No 1=Yes

If yes, how often do you meet your close friends?

- 0=Never
- 1=Less than once a month
- 2=Once a month
- 3=Few times per month
- 4=Few times per week
- 5=Everyday/Daily

6. What foreign languages are you skilled at?

- 1. I don't speak any foreign language.
- 2. |__| Reading |__| Speaking |__| Writing
- 3. |__| Reading |__| Speaking |__| Writing
- 4. |__| Reading |__| Speaking |__| Writing

7. Please mark your answer on the scale which applies to you.

Things that happen in my life most often depend on

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Circumstances, situations, and other people											My own decisions, efforts, and behaviour.

8. To what extent do you feel responsible for your health?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
To very little extent										To a great extent

Questions suggested for inclusion in the final baseline questionnaire version for WP3 to harmonize with WP2 and WP4

- Marital status
- |__| Single
- |__| Divorced/Separated
- |__| Married
- |__| Living with a partner but not married, cohabiting

- Household members

Household population	<input type="radio"/> 1
<input type="radio"/> 2-4	<input type="radio"/> >4
<input type="radio"/> Children: _____	

WP5 Specific Questions

9. Would you describe your diet as healthy?

0 = No; 1 = Somewhat; 2 = Yes

10. Which statement would best describe your health status?

|__| I generally feel absolutely healthy.

|__| I only experience minor health issues from time to time.

|__| I have major and/or chronic health issues.

|__| I am constantly sick.

11. Which statement would best describe your understanding of health, health practices, and health issues?

- |__| I am fully aware of my health issues and also have a solid understanding of other health matters.
- |__| I am fully aware of my health issues, their causes, and how I should take care of myself.
- |__| I understand I have some health issues, but I don't know exactly why and what to do about it.
- |__| My doctor tells me that I have severe health issues, but I do not really understand what it means and what I should do with this.

12. Do you have savings/financial funds that (in case of losing your income) could cover your expenses for at least 3 subsequent months?

0=No 1=Yes

13. Do you have a group of close friends you feel you belong to?

0=No 1=Yes

If yes, how often do you meet your close friends?

0=Never

1=Less than once a month

2=Once a month

3=Few times per month

4=Few times per week

5=Everyday/Daily

14. What foreign languages are you skilled at?

5. I don't speak any foreign language.

6. |__| Reading |__| Speaking |__| Writing

7. |__| Reading |__| Speaking |__| Writing

8. |__| Reading |__| Speaking |__| Writing

15. Please mark your answer on the scale which applies to you.

Things that happen in my life most often depend on

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Circumstances, situations, and other people											My own decisions, efforts, and behaviour.

16. To what extent do you feel responsible for your health?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
To very little extent											To a great extent

Questions suggested for inclusion in the final baseline questionnaire version for WP4 to harmonize with WP2, and WP3

- Marital status. Please kindly add cohabitation (Living with a partner but not married) as a separate option to the possible answers.
- Living place rural vs province

Current address:	<input type="radio"/> Province: _____
<input type="radio"/> Rural	<input type="radio"/> Urban

- Family history of cancer

Family:

First degree relative has/ had cancer (mark all concerned):	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No
<input type="radio"/> Mother	<input type="radio"/> Father	
<input type="radio"/> Brother/ Sister	<input type="radio"/> Grandparents	
If YES, please mention where the cancer was localized:		
<input type="radio"/> Stomach	<input type="radio"/> Colorectal	
<input type="radio"/> Breast	<input type="radio"/> Not sure	
<input type="radio"/> Other: _____		

- Comorbidity diseases/medical history.
- For example: Does a worker have some comorbidity diseases such as hypertension, diabetes, tuberculosis etc.?

- Diet

- How often do you usually eat the following food items?
- 1=never
- 2=less than once a month 3=1-3 times a month 4=once or twice a week
- 5=most days but not every days 6=every day
- 9=unknown/refuse to answer
- |__| Red meat (i.e. beef, veal, pork, lamb, mutton, horse, and goat meat) If red meat consumed:
- |__| Poultry (i.e. chicken and turkey)
- |__| Processed* meat, including hams, salami, sausages, etc.
- |__| Fish
- |__| Fresh fruits (i.e. apples, pears, orange and other citrus fruits, bananas, berries, etc.)
- |__| Raw vegetables (i.e. green salads, tomatoes, etc., when in season)
- |__| Cooked green/leafy vegetables (i.e. spinach, artichokes, asparagus, green beans, etc.)
- |__| Dairy products (i.e. milk, yoghurts, cheese, butter, etc.)
- |__| Cookies, biscuits, chocolates, cakes and sweets
- |__| Soft drinks (eg cola)

*Salted, smoked, or processed with any other preservation method.

- Smoking. Does a worker smoke and how much and how often?

1. Did you smoke cigarettes in the past year? |__|
(0=No, 1=Yes, 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

1.1.1 How many cigarettes per day on average? (ignore pipe or cigar smoking; "cigarettes" include handrolled) |__|__|

1.1.2 At what age did you start smoking? (i.e. using cigarettes on most days) |__|__|

1.1.3 How many years have you smoked? |__|__|

If no:

1.1.4 Have you ever smoked cigarettes on most days for at least one year? (0=No,1=Yes, 9=refuse to answer)

1.1.5 How many cigarettes did you smoke per day on average? (ignore pipe and cigar smoking; "cigarettes" include handrolled) |__|__|

1.1.6 At what age did you start smoking on most days? |__|__|

1.1.7 At what age did you stop smoking? |__|__|

•

- Source of health information seeking.
- Please kindly add social media as a separate option in the answers.

WP5 Specific Questions

17. Would you describe your diet as healthy?

0 = No; 1 = Somewhat; 2 = Yes

18. Which statement would best describe your health status?

|__| I generally feel absolutely healthy.

|__| I only experience minor health issues from time to time.

|__| I have major and/or chronic health issues.

|__| I am constantly sick.

19. Which statement would best describe your understanding of health, health practices, and health issues?

- |__| I am fully aware of my health issues and also have a solid understanding of other health matters.
- |__| I am fully aware of my health issues, their causes, and how I should take care of myself.
- |__| I understand I have some health issues, but I don't know exactly why and what to do about it.
- |__| My doctor tells me that I have severe health issues, but I do not really understand what it means and what I should do with this.

20. Do you have savings/financial funds that (in case of losing your income) could cover your expenses for at least 3 subsequent months?

0=No 1=Yes

21. Do you have a group of close friends you feel you belong to?

0=No 1=Yes

If yes, how often do you meet your close friends?

0=Never

1=Less than once a month

2=Once a month

3=Few times per month

4=Few times per week

5=Everyday/Daily

22. What foreign languages are you skilled at?

9. I don't speak any foreign language.

10. |__| Reading |__| Speaking |__| Writing

11. |__| Reading |__| Speaking |__| Writing

12. |__| Reading |__| Speaking |__| Writing

23. Please mark your answer on the scale which applies to you.

Things that happen in my life most often depend on

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Circumstances, situations, and other people											My own decisions, efforts, and behaviour.

24. To what extent do you feel responsible for your health?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
To very little extent										To a great extent

4 Protocol for self-administered projective technique

Projective Technique to Assess Worker's Self-Perceived Health Capital

CPW WP5 Research Protocol

Projective techniques are an approach to gaining insights into people's understandings and imageries in contexts where the response to a direct questionnaire may be complex to obtain or where socially acceptable, but not necessarily truthful responses might be expected. There is a wide range of projective techniques with a common origin in clinical psychiatry that have been adapted and are currently being used in social sciences. Projective techniques are employed in varying degrees in consumer, education, and health research since they allow participants to express those thoughts and feelings that can be difficult to access by direct questioning. This is achieved by presenting participants with ambiguous verbal or visual stimulus materials. Importantly, projective techniques can also be fun and therefore engaging for participants to perform (Belk, Ger & Askegaard 1997; Catterall & Ibbotson, 2000; Gambaro, 2018; Wiehagen et al., 2007).

Therefore, projective techniques might be a suitable methodology to be employed for research on health-related topics in different cultural settings, particularly in those settings where qualitative data collection might prove difficult because of the language barrier. *The aim of using the expression as projective circle technique is to explore workers' perceptions of the social, cultural, economic resources, and personal antecedents constituting their health capital* (Schneider-Kamp, 2021; Schneider-Kamp et al. 2021; Schneider-Kamp and Askegaard, 2022; Schneider-Kamp et al. 2023). See **Figure 1** for an illustration of the patient-centric parts of the health capital model.

Figure 1. The health capital model underlying the proposed projective circle technique.

Procedure: After filling the baseline questionnaire, participants will be asked to perform a projective technique task. Using the proposed projective circle technique, the participants will be asked to think about different health-related aspects that serve as proxies for the resources that comprise health capital. The participants are tasked to draw these aspects as the smaller circles inside the bigger circle which represents their overall health. The collected data will be sent by post to SDU researchers, where it will be coded in terms of the relative size of different circles drawn by the participants. This means that each circle size is coded by comparing it with other circle sizes inside the big circle which represents the overall health of a participant. The sizes are coded into up to 3 categories: *large*, *medium*, and *small*. Then this data will be analysed together with the data collected through the baseline questionnaire.

Tools: Paper and pencil

Method: self-administered

Participants: N=300

Duration: 5-10 min

The address where the collected data should be sent is:

Department of Business and Management
Att. Anna Schneider-Kamp & Tija Rageliene
Campusvej 55
5230 Odense M
Denmark

Instructions to the participant (worded as clearly and simple as possible):

Consider the big circle below as a representation of your general health. Examine the provided list and indicate the importance you attribute to each item for your health within the big circle. Use circles of varying sizes to signify their importance. If you find something in the list that you think is not important for your health, please draw a circle outside the big circle that represents your overall health. Please label each circle you draw with the corresponding number from the list. For example, if someone considers their age highly relevant to their health, their job role somewhat relevant, their dog somewhat relevant but to a smaller degree than the job role, and their neighbours not relevant at all, that person might draw something like this:

Example list and drawing.

1. My age
2. My job role
3. My dog
4. My neighbours

Now, please proceed as follows: First, examine the list numbered 1 to 12 below. Then, draw the circles to illustrate the importance of each item to your health. Finally, label each circle with the corresponding number from the list.

How important are each of these for your health?

1. Relationships with my friends.
2. Relationships with my family members.
3. Diseases in my family's history.
4. Communication with health care specialists (for ex. GP, nurses, doctors, etc.)
5. Government attention/support to the health care system.
6. Availability of information about health and diseases.
7. My educational background.
8. Foreign languages I can understand.
9. Access to digital technologies (e.g., smartphone, computer fitness tracker)
10. Money for buying medicine and paying for health services.
11. Money for purchasing healthy high-quality foods (e.g., organic, ecological)
12. How well I can handle stress.

Example of the task performed.

My Health

Protocol to be translated into the local language and given to the participants.

Participant's ID _____

Gender: Male Female Other

Age: _____

Consider the big circle below as a representation of your general health. Examine the provided list and indicate the importance you attribute to each item for your health within the big circle. Use circles of varying sizes to signify their importance. If you find something in the list that you think is not important for your health, please draw a circle outside the big circle that represents your overall health. Please label each circle you draw with the corresponding number from the list. For example, if someone considers their age highly relevant to their health, their job role somewhat relevant, their dog somewhat relevant but to a smaller degree than the job role, and their neighbours not relevant at all, that person might draw something like this:

Example list and drawing.

1. My age
2. My job role
3. My dog
4. My neighbours

Now, please proceed as follows: First, examine the list numbered 1 to 12 below. Then, draw the circles to illustrate the importance of each item to your health. Finally, label each circle with the corresponding number from the list.

How important are each of these for your health?

1. Relationships with my friends
2. Relationships with my family members
3. Diseases in my family's history
4. Communication with health care specialists (for ex. GP, nurses, doctors, etc.)
5. Government attention/support to the health care system
6. Availability of information about health and diseases
7. My educational background
8. Foreign languages I can understand.
9. Access to digital technologies (e.g., smartphone, computer fitness tracker)
10. Money for buying medicine and paying for health services.
11. Money for purchasing healthy high-quality foods (e.g., organic, ecological)
12. How well I can handle stress.

My Health

References:

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5 Final English version of self-administered projective technique

My health

Participant's ID:

Gender: Male Female Other

Age:

Consider the big circle below as a representation of your general health. Examine the provided list and indicate the importance you attribute to each item for your health within the big circle. Use circles of varying sizes to signify their importance. If you find something in the list that you think is not important for your health, please draw a circle outside the big circle that represents your overall health. Please label each circle you draw with the corresponding number from the list. For example, if someone considers their age highly relevant to their health, their job role somewhat relevant, their dog somewhat relevant but to a smaller degree than the job role, and their neighbors not relevant at all, that person might draw something like this:

Example list and drawing.

My health

1. My age
2. My job role
3. My dog
4. My neighbors

Now, please proceed as follows: First, examine the list numbered 1 to 12 below. Then, draw the circles to illustrate the importance of each item to your health. Finally, label each circle with the corresponding number from the list.

My health

How important are each of these for your health?

1. Relationships with my friends.
2. Relationships with my family members.
3. Diseases in my family's history.
4. Communication with health care specialists
(For example, GP, nurses, doctors, etc.).
5. Government attention/support to the health care system.
6. Availability of information about health and diseases.
7. My educational background.
8. Foreign languages I can understand.
9. Access to digital technologies
(For example, smartphone, computer fitness tracker).
10. Money for buying medicine and paying for health services.
11. Money for purchasing healthy high-quality foods
(For example, organic, ecological).
12. How well I can handle stress.

6 Final Italian version of self-administered projective technique

La mia salute

Codice identificativo:

Sesso: Maschio Femmina Altro

Età:

Consideri il grande cerchio sottostante come una rappresentazione della sua salute generale. Esami l'elenco fornito e indichi l'importanza attribuita a ciascun aspetto per la sua salute all'interno del grande cerchio. Utilizzi cerchi di varie dimensioni per indicare la loro importanza. Scriva dentro ogni cerchio il numero corrispondente dall'elenco. Se ritiene che qualche aspetto dell'elenco non sia importante per la sua salute, disegni un cerchio al di fuori del grande cerchio che rappresenta la sua salute complessiva. Scriva quindi all'interno di ogni cerchio il corrispondente numero dell'elenco.

Ad esempio, se lei considera la sua età molto rilevante per la sua salute, il suo ruolo lavorativo in qualche modo rilevante, il suo cane di un grado meno rilevante del suo ruolo lavorativo, e i suoi vicini per nulla rilevanti, lei potrebbe disegnare qualcosa del genere:

Elenco di esempio e disegno.

La mia salute

1. La mia età
2. Il mio ruolo lavorativo
3. Il mio cane
4. I miei vicini

Ora, si prega di procedere come segue: in primo luogo, esamini l'elenco numerato da 1 a 12 nella pagina seguente. Poi, disegni i cerchi per illustrare l'importanza di ogni aspetto per la sua salute. Infine, scriva dentro ogni cerchio il numero corrispondente dall'elenco.

La mia salute

Quanto sono importanti i seguenti aspetti per la sua salute?

1. Rapporti con i miei amici.
2. Rapporti con i miei familiari.
3. Malattie nella storia della mia famiglia.
4. Comunicazione con professionisti sanitari (ad es. MMG, medici, infermieri).
5. Attenzione/sostegno del governo al sistema sanitario.
6. Disponibilità di informazioni su salute e malattie.
7. Il mio livello di istruzione.
8. Lingue straniere che posso capire.
9. Disponibilità di tecnologie digitali (ad es. smartphone, PC, smartwatch).
10. Disponibilità economica per comprare medicine e per accedere alle visite mediche.
11. Disponibilità economica per comprare cibo salutare di elevata qualità (ad es. cibo biologico, ecologico).
12. Come so gestire lo stress.

7 Final Romanian version of self-administered projective technique

Sănătatea mea

ID Participant:

Gen: Masculin Feminin Altul

Vârsta:

Luată în considerare cercul mare de mai jos ca o reprezentare a stării dumneavoastră generale de sănătate. Examinați lista oferită și indicați importanța pe care o atribuiți fiecărui element pentru sănătatea dumneavoastră în cadrul cercului mare. Folosiți cercuri de dimensiuni diferite pentru a indica importanța lor. Etichetați fiecare cerc cu numărul corespunzător din listă. De exemplu, dacă un participant consideră că vârsta lui este foarte relevantă pentru sănătatea sa, rolul său la muncă oarecum relevant și vecinii săi aproape irelevanți, acel participant ar putea desena ceva de genul acesta:

Exemplu de listă și desen:

Sănătatea mea

1. Vârsta mea
2. Locul meu de muncă
3. Câinele meu
4. Vecinii mei

Acum, vă rugăm să procedați după cum urmează: Mai întâi, examinați lista numerotată de la 1 la 12 de mai jos. Apoi, desenați cercurile pentru a ilustra importanța fiecărui element pentru sănătatea dumneavoastră. În cele din urmă, etichetați fiecare cerc cu numărul corespunzător din listă.

Sănătatea mea

Cât de importante sunt fiecare dintre acestea pentru sănătatea ta?

1. Relațiile cu prietenii mei.
2. Relațiile cu membrii familiei mele.
3. Boli din istoria familiei mele.
4. Comunicarea cu specialiștii din domeniul sănătății (de ex. medic de familie, asistente medicale, medici etc.).
5. Atenția/sprijinul guvernului pentru sistemul de sănătate.
6. Disponibilitatea informațiilor despre sănătate și boli.
7. Contextul meu educațional.
8. Limbi străine pe care le pot înțelege.
9. Acces la tehnologii digitale (de exemplu, smartphone, monitor de fitness pe computer).
10. Bani pentru cumpărarea medicamentelor și plata serviciilor de sănătate.
11. Bani pentru achiziționarea de alimente sănătoase de înaltă calitate (de exemplu, organice, ecologice).
12. Cât de bine pot face față stresului.

8 Final Slovak version of self-administered projective technique

Moje zdravie

ID účastníka:

Pohlavie: Muž Žena Iné

Vek:

Považujte veľký kruh nižšie ako reprezentáciu vášho celkového zdravia. Preskúmajte poskytnutý zoznam a vo veľkom kruhu označte dôležitosť, ktorú pripisujete každej položke pre svoje zdravie. Použite kruhy rôznych veľkostí na vyjadrenie ich dôležitosti. Ak nájdete v zozname niečo, o čom si myslíte, že nie je dôležité pre vaše zdravie, nakreslite kruh mimo veľkého kruhu, ktorý predstavuje vaše celkové zdravie. Označte každý kruh, ktorý nakreslíte, príslušným číslom zo zoznamu.

Napríklad, ak niekto považuje svoj vek za veľmi dôležitý pre zdravie, ich pracovnú rolu do istej miery relevantnú pre zdravie, ich psa do istej miery relevantného pre zdravie, ale v menšej miere ako pracovná úloha, a ich susedov nepovažuje vôbec za relevantných pre svoje zdravie potom táto osoba by mohla nakresliť niečo takéto:

Príklad zoznamu a nákresu:

Moje zdravie

1. Môj vek
2. Moja pracovná úloha
3. Môj pes
4. Môj sused

Teraz, prosím, postupujte nasledovne:

Najprv si pozrite zoznam položiek očíslovaný 1 až 12 ako je uvedené nižšie. Potom nakreslite rôzne veľké kruhy, aby ste ilustrovali dôležitosť každej z uvedených položiek pre vaše zdravie. Nakoniec označte každý kruh zodpovedajúcim číslom zo zoznamu.

Moje zdravie

Aké dôležité je každé z uvedených položiek pre vaše zdravie:

1. Vzťahy s mojimi priateľmi.
2. Vzťahy s členmi mojej rodiny.
3. Choroby, ktoré sa vyskytli v mojej rodine.
4. Komunikácia so zdravotníkmi špecialistami (napr. všeobecný lekár, zdravotné sestry, lekári atď.).
5. Vládna pozornosť/podpora systému zdravotnej starostlivosti.
6. Dostupnosť informácií o zdraví a chorobách.
7. Moje vzdelanie.
8. Cudzie jazyky, ktorým rozumiem.
9. Prístup k digitálnym technológiám (Napríklad smartfón, počítačový "fitness tracker").
10. Peniaze na nákup liekov a zaplatenie zdravotníckych služieb.
11. Peniaze na nákup zdravých a kvalitných potravín (Napríklad organické, ekologické).
12. Ako dobre zvládam stres.

9 Protocol for projective techniques during focus groups

Projective Techniques to Assess Worker's Self-Perceived Health Capital and Paths to Cancer Prevention

CPW WP5 Research Protocol

Projective techniques are an approach to gaining insights into people's perceptions and behaviour in contexts where the response to a direct questionnaire may be complex to obtain or where socially acceptable, but not necessarily truthful responses might be expected. There is a wide range of projective techniques with a common origin in clinical psychiatry that have been adapted and are currently being used in social sciences. Projective techniques are employed in varying degrees in consumer, education, and health research since they allow participants to express those thoughts and feelings that can be difficult to access by direct questioning. This is achieved by presenting participants with ambiguous verbal or visual stimulus materials. Importantly, projective techniques can also be fun and engaging for participants to perform (Catterall & Ibbotson, 2000; Gambaro, 2018; Wiehagen et al., 2007).

Therefore, projective techniques might be a suitable methodology to be employed for research on health-related topics in different cultural settings, particularly in those settings where qualitative data collection might prove difficult because of the language barrier. The aim of the focus groups is *to understand barriers and facilitators for infection-related cancer prevention in the population of workers using projective techniques as the method for qualitative data collection*. The projective techniques employed include, but are not limited, to association, ordering, and expression.

Participants: N=12

Note: Participants should bring their smartphones or tablets to the session

Duration: 90 min

Tools and facilities needed for focus group implementation:

- Quiet and pleasant room with a round table for 15 people (12 participants, 2 researchers, 1 mediator/translator).
- Freely available Wi-Fi connection and password to join the internet.
- Printed materials with the tasks on paper arcs.
- Little snacks such as fruits, cookies, and/or little pastries.
- Water and glasses.
- Recording equipment (brought by the researchers)

Task 1. Association and ordering

Time: 20 min

Instructions: Participants are given paper and pencil and are asked to write all the words that come to their minds related to either the word “health” and “cancer prevention”. Then participants are asked to rank the top 5 most important words from those they wrote down.

Example:

Follow-up questions for the “Health” concept:

1. What associations come to your mind when you think about “health”? What is “health” for you? What does health mean for you?
2. Which words do you label as the top 5 words? Why?

Follow-up questions for the “Cancer prevention” concept:

1. What associations come to your mind about “cancer prevention”? What is “cancer prevention” for you? What does “cancer prevention” mean for you?
2. Which words do you label as the top 5 words? Why?

Task 2. Expression through drawing

Time: 30 min

Instructions to the participant (worded as clearly and simple as possible):

Consider the big circle below as a representation of your general health. Examine the provided list and indicate the importance you attribute to each item for your health within the big circle. Use circles of varying sizes to signify their importance. If you find something in the list that you think is not important for your health, please draw a circle outside the big circle that represents your overall health. Please label each circle you draw with the corresponding number from the list. For example, if someone considers their age highly relevant to their health, their job role somewhat relevant, their dog somewhat relevant but to a smaller degree than the job role, and their neighbours not relevant at all, that person might draw something like this:

Example list and drawing.

1. My age
2. My job role
3. My dog
4. My neighbours

Now, please proceed as follows: First, examine the list numbered 1 to 12 below. Then, draw the circles to illustrate the importance of each item to your health. Finally, label each circle with the corresponding number from the list.

How important are each of these for your health?

1. Relationships with my friends
2. Relationships with my family members
3. Diseases in my family's history
4. Communication with health care specialists (for ex. GP, nurses, doctors, etc.)
5. Government attention/support to the health care system
6. Availability of information about health and diseases
7. My educational background
8. Foreign languages I can understand.
9. Access to digital technologies (e.g., smartphone, computer fitness tracker)
10. Money for buying medicine and paying for health services.
11. Money for purchasing healthy high-quality foods (e.g., organic, ecological)
12. How well I can handle stress.

Example of the task performed.

My Health

Follow-up semi-structured interview questions for focus group participants

1. Which numbers/items from the list have the 3 biggest circles in your drawing? What do the 3 biggest circles that you draw represent?
2. Why do you think/ these 3 things (name the items that the participants mentioned while answering question number 1) are important for your health? How?
3. Can you tell an example from your life when (item that participant mentioned) was related to your health?
4. Which numbers/items from the list have the 3 smallest circles in your drawing?
5. Why do you think these 3 items are the least important for your health? Please share an example from your life.

10 min break

Task 3. Workers Pathways to Cancer Prevention

Time: 30 min

Participants are presented with a scenario and asked about their actions, attitudes, and feelings in terms of the scenario presented to them. The goal of this task is to understand workers' pathways to infection related to cancer prevention and identify barriers and facilitators of prevention of infection related to cancer.

Instructions to the participants:

Scenario 1. Hepatitis C virus

You just find out that you are in a risk group of getting the hepatitis C virus because you were informed that at the dentist's office, the accident might have happened when a dentist assistant accidentally used not completely sterile equipment and had blood contact involved during your visit while repairing your tooth. Please picture/describe the steps you would take in this situation to avoid liver cancer since you know that hepatitis C virus infection might lead to liver cancer if not treated on time.

Scenario 2. Helicobacter pylori infection

Your employer has just informed you that you are at risk of getting Helicobacter pylori bacteria which if not treated can lead to gastric cancer. You are at risk since one of your co-workers that you used to eat your lunch with was found infected with Helicobacter pylori, and some hygiene-related issues were found in the food catering services which facilities you use to have your lunch with co-workers. Please think and include if relevant your immediate actions, plans/actions for the future, and your daily activities/lifestyle activities while performing this task.

Follow-up questions:

1. What would be your first thoughts in this situation? How do you think you would feel?
2. What would be the first thing you think you would do? Why?
3. What would be the next step/steps? Why do you think this/these step/steps is/are important?
4. What would be the last step you would do in this situation? Why?
5. How would you feel after performing this last step?
6. How do you think you would succeed in preventing hepatitis C infection and/or liver cancer?

10 Thematic interview guide for focus groups

List of themes based on the WP5-specific questions for the baseline questionnaires.		
Theme	Topics for discussion	Comments
Marital status	Quality of relationships with partner/spouse, responsibility for health decision making	
Household members	People living together with the study participant, household composition, time spent together with the household members, health habits of household members (diet, smoking, alcohol use, etc.).	
Diseases in the family	Family history of cancer, other significant diseases in the family or origin (first degree relatives: parents, siblings, uncles, aunts).	
Living place	The access to health care facilities in rural or urban place, access to quality food, access to gym, safety of neighbourhood, etc.	
Health/Lifestyle habits	Diet, consumption of alcohol, smoking, drugs, etc.	
Health status	Individually perceived health status, medical history, current diseases, comorbidity diseases, understanding of health, health practices, and personal health issues.	
Health information seeking	Practices of seeking health information, sources of health information seeking.	
Responsibility of own's health	Perception of own's responsibility regarding own's health, how one's behaviour, decision-making, attitude impacts one's health.	
Languages	Languages the participant can speak, the degree to which participant can speak a foreign language.	
Financial stability	Income and savings participant has, the way participant generate his/her income, strategies one has for managing his/her finances.	
Close friends	Friendships participant has, perception of close friendship, feeling belonging to friends' group.	
List of themes based on the preliminary results of the systematic literature review.		
Theme	Topics for discussion	Comments
<i>Social factors</i>		
Health of family members	Health decision making in the family, caregiving to a family member or members, family support for prevention of infections related to cancer.	
Experience of stigma related to infections and vaccination	Stigma associated with vaccination, feelings of shame and stigma, perceived discrimination	
Occupation and health care practices in the workplace	Participant's occupation/profession, check-ups and examinations organized by employer if any.	
Marital status	Relationship status, plans to change relationship status if any, if there are some recent changes in marital status.	
Social networks	Belonging to various social groups in the community, for example, religious organizations or others. Health information spreading with these social networks if any.	

Theme	Topics for discussion	Comments
<i>Cultural factors</i>		
Trust in health care systems	Trust in the government and health care systems, trust in medical doctors and medical care services, quality of health care.	
Health experiences of vaccination and screening	Fear of cancer diagnosis and test results, fear of doctors, fear of medical and testing procedures, fear of male practitioners (for women only), fear of potential discomfort caused by the examination (HPV).	
Communication and interaction with health care professionals	Experience of recommendation and counselling by doctor/health care providers, experience of preventive care in the healthcare practice, linguistic discordance if any, linguistic ability to communicate with the health care professionals.	
Experience of previous health conditions	History of experiencing gynaecological or other physical conditions before felt the higher need of getting vaccinated (for women only regarding HPV).	
Health policy practices	Satisfaction with the health care system, flexible treatment access, careful and considered treatment practices.	
Knowledge of infections related to cancer and their prevention	Knowledge and awareness about HPV, HBV, HCV, Hp, getting the information about on infections and their consequences, knowledge of infections-related cancer, acquiring information on vaccines, knowing about benefits of screening and where to get screened or how to get vaccinated, awareness of available treatments from infections.	
<i>Economic factors</i>		
Personal finance	Financial resources and income of participants, health insurance situation and health insurance costs, possibility to take treatment and save employment while taking the treatment (relevant for HCV positive workers only).	
Health care costs	Cost of the vaccines and screening and how they are covered (insurance vs. out-of-pocket costs), time and travel costs, health care costs, availability of transportation and transportation costs to a health care centre.	
Health policy and coverage of the costs	Availability/existence of government-funded programs for free or reduced-cost screening and vaccinations (HPV), convenient vaccination practices, availability for vaccination and screening (enough health care centres and health care workers to provide health care services)	
<i>Personal factors</i>		
Age of receiving vaccination	Participant's history of undergoing vaccination programs	
Sexual behaviour	Contraceptive use, sexual habits, age of sexual debut.	
Physical condition	Experiencing symptoms of cancer-related infections if any, current self-perceived health status, experiencing side effects of treatment (relevant for HCV positive workers only).	
Perception of threat and self-perceived susceptibility to infections related to cancer	Perceived worthiness of getting vaccine due to experiences of sexual activities (HPV), perceived susceptibility and risk of infection, self-rated health status, beliefs about the benefits of vaccination, understanding the potentially severe long-term consequences of HCV (HCV infection specific).	

Table 5. Thematic interview guide.

References:

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